

Assessment and improvement of n-paraffin distribution obtained by HTGC to predict accurately crude oil cold properties

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Abstract

Wax precipitation and deposition in crude oils can produce flow assurance problems in production and transportation operations. Knowledge of the wax appearance temperature (WAT) and the amount of wax that precipitates from the crude oil at different temperatures, i.e. the wax precipitation curve (WPC) is necessary for accurate predictions of wax deposition in subsea pipelines. The theoretical study of wax precipitation process is frequently carried out using thermodynamic models. These models require as input information the molecular weight and the n-paraffin distribution of the crude oil. The n-paraffin distribution is commonly determined by high temperature gas-chromatography (HTGC) analysis, but it has some limitations such as the low signal/noise ratios, elution and resolution problems in the heavy compounds zone and discrepancies with regard to the delineation of the baseline to integrate the chromatogram. In this work, three variables have been analyzed to improve the n-paraffin distribution obtained by HTGC: the total amount of C_{20}^+ paraffin, the extrapolation of paraffin concentration above C_{38}^+ , and the molecular weight of crude oil. The results predicted were compared to experimental data obtained by fractional precipitation and differential scanning calorimetry, showing a great influence of the n-paraffin distribution on the model accuracy.

Keywords: Wax precipitation, High Temperature Gas Chromatography, solid-liquid equilibrium, n-paraffin distribution, flow assurance.

1. Introduction

Paraffin waxes contained in petroleum mixtures can precipitate when temperature decreases during oil production, transport through pipelines or storage. Such problem is very well known within the petroleum industry because the presence of solid waxes increases fluid viscosity and its accumulation on the wall reduces the flow line section, causing the blockage of filters, valves and pipelines and reducing or even stopping oil production or transportation. All these facts increase operational costs and are identified as “flow assurance problems”. Consequently, a great effort has been made to understand, describe and predict the wax formation process ¹⁻³.

Crude oils are complex mixtures formed by a great variety of compounds and the determination of their composition is impossible. The solubility of such different species in a crude oil depends on pressure, temperature and crude oil composition. Waxes are usually considered to be heavy hydrocarbons (C₂₀-C₆₀) mainly formed by linear n-alkanes ⁴ and represent the major risks in wax deposition problems because they can precipitate when the temperature of the crude oil decreases due to the reduction of their solubility.

The prediction of the wax appearance temperature (WAT) and the wax precipitation curve (WPC) of crude oils is critical to avoid or minimize flow assurance problems related to wax deposition in flow lines or storage tanks ^{5, 6}. Thermodynamic models should provide that information, while kinetic models should estimate the deposition rate and the thickness of the layer of deposit. Nevertheless, predicted results by kinetic models are strongly influenced by the reliability of the thermodynamic ones.

Some thermodynamic models of wax precipitation process require as input data the knowledge of the n-paraffin distribution, the total wax content (C₂₀⁺) and the

molecular weight of the crude oil. Obtaining the distribution of n-paraffin is not an easy task. There are several methods to determine it, but the most widely used are those based on high temperature gas chromatography^{3, 7, 8}.

One of the major unsolved problems in obtaining the n-paraffin distribution by HTGC is the uncertainty in the determination of the baseline to integrate the chromatogram due to the low signal/noise ratios and the interference created by other components of different nature, which makes the integration process difficult. In addition, heavy n-paraffins can be eluted with difficulty, so the wrong determination of their composition affects the WAT value. To overcome some of these difficulties, the isolation of saturated compounds was proposed in the literature⁹. Also, two integration methods have been tested: valley to valley integration and integration to the baseline of the chromatogram¹⁰.

Different experimental methods to determine cold properties of crude oils have been reported in the literature¹¹⁻¹⁹. Most currently used methods are indirect, i. e. the change in a property of the sample which is known to be affected by wax precipitation is measured. However, the result of such methods is determined by the accuracy in the measurement of the property in question. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is a fast technique that provides good results¹⁸. It measures the variation in heat flow between a sample of crude oil and a reference, or the power that must be provided or removed from the system for both, sample and reference remain at the same temperature when the crude oil is subjected to a temperature profile in a controlled atmosphere. In this work it has been used to determine the WAT and the WPC of crude oils.

Several procedures exist for the direct determination of the total amount of waxes and the WPC. In most cases, precipitated wax is separated from the rest of the crude oil by filtering and quantifying by gravimetry. One of these is a modification of

the traditional Burger's method ¹¹ which provides the total wax content (C_{20}^+) in a crude oil, because it is widely accepted that all paraffinic compounds which can lead to flow assurance problems ($C_{20} - C_{60}$) precipitate at -20 °C. Nevertheless, it can not be used to determine WPC because it presents two limitations: the starting crude oil sample is dissolved and it can be only used to study wax precipitation at a single temperature. An alternative method, known as the fractional precipitation method, overcomes such limitations ¹⁵. In this method, crude oil is not dissolved in any solvent, and it consists of making consecutive filtration experiments while reducing the operation temperature. Finally, trapped crude oil into the precipitated paraffinic solid must be quantified to obtain the WPC. For example, Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance can be used for that purpose ¹⁶.

In this work, the saturate fraction of one crude oil was extracted using a SARA type analysis based on the ASTM D 2549-02 ¹⁷. The n-paraffin distribution of the raw crude oil was determined by HTGC from its saturate fraction. The molecular weight of the crude oil was obtained by gel permeation chromatography. A predictive model ²¹⁻³⁶ was applied to calculate the WPC of the crude oil using the n-paraffin distribution previously determined. Model predictions were checked with experimental data of wax precipitation (WAT and WPC) obtained by fractional precipitation ^{9, 15} and differential scanning calorimetry ^{9, 20}.

Predictions were greatly influenced by the integration method used to determine the n-paraffin distribution fed to the model. Apart from the integration method, different variables were studied such as the total C_{20}^+ paraffin content, the concentration of n-paraffin compounds from C_{38}^+ and the molecular weight of the crude oil.

It was shown that the best agreement was achieved when using the n-paraffin distribution obtained by integration method from valley to the baseline together with the

amount of waxes C_{20}^+ . Elution problems were overcome taking into account the WAT obtained by DSC. The results show that the experimental error in the determination of molecular weight has a negligible effect on the predictions.

2. Experimental and Computational Section

Materials. A dead paraffinic crude oil from Asia provided by Repsol was used in this work.

Gravimetric determination of wax precipitation. Two procedures have been used for experimental determination of wax precipitation in this work: modified Burger's method¹¹ and fractional precipitation¹⁵. In the first method, crude oil is dissolved in n-pentane and stirred during 30 min. A mixture of acetone – n-pentane (3:1 vol/vol) is added to the mixture and cooled down to -20 °C for 12 h. The solid phase present in the oil is separated by filtration in a Buchner funnel using a glass microfibre Whatman filter N° 934. The solid phase is washed with n-pentane in order to remove asphaltenes and the filtered liquid evaporated. This solid obtained after solvent evaporation contains the n-paraffins and is re-dissolved in n-hexane and filtered again. After solvent removal the final product is weighted.

The fractional precipitation of paraffins contained in a crude oil consists of making consecutive filtration experiments while reducing the working temperature. The crude oil sample is cooled in a cryostat at a lower temperature than its WAT for 24 h. It is then filtered using a glass microfibre Whatman filter N° 934 during at least 2 h. The solid phase is collected for further purification of the precipitated waxes while the liquid phase is used for the next precipitation. The solid phase is washed with acetone to reduce the trapped crude oil. This washing process is carried out at room temperature in a Buchner funnel using vacuum. The remaining solids are recovered by washing the

filter with dichloromethane, and after solvent removal by heating at 50 - 60 °C the final free-solvent product is weighted and stored for further characterization.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). This technique is usually used to experimentally quantify the amount of wax precipitated in crude oils ^{4, 11, 37}. The equipment used to carry out the calorimetric measurements was a DSC822e from Mettler Toledo. In DSC analysis the sample follows a temperature profile, the heat transfer is registered, and any phase transition is quantified through the involved heat change. The difference between the DSC curve and the baseline is a direct measurement of the total heat involved in the phase change, which is converted into the corresponding mass using a calibration from pure n-paraffins. In a previous work ²⁰, experimental DSC conditions were optimized for this kind of samples. First, the sample is heated from 20 to 80 °C at 3 °C/min. Then, the sample is cooled from 80 to -120 °C at 3 °C/min, and finally, the sample is heated from -120 to 80 °C at the same rate.

The baseline is determined by assuming that the sample behaves as a usual liquid at temperatures above the WAT and as a solid-like at very low temperatures and that the two-phase system behaviour can be obtained by imposing the continuity of the heat capacity and first derivative. DSC measured heat is converted into mass through the specific melting heat ^{4, 20, 38}.

SARA type separation. The purpose of this method focuses on determining the content of saturated, aromatics, resins and asphaltenes in a crude oil. It is based on the ASTM D 2549-02 standard test method ¹⁷ with some modifications, related to the removal of asphaltenes and the stationary phases used. In the first stage of SARA type analysis asphaltenes and insoluble resins should be separated by precipitation with n-pentane (crude oil/solvent ratio equal to 1/30 vol.). The filtered sample (malthene fraction) is

later split up in a chromatographic column to obtain saturated compounds, aromatic and polar resins.

Chromatographic separation of malthenes is carried out in an installation that comprises three glass columns packed with silica gel (Macherey-Nagel 0.071-0.160 mm / 100-200 mesh) and alumina (Merck 0.063-0.200 mm / 70-230 mesh). A stream of nitrogen is also used to control liquid flow through the columns. In two of them, crude oil samples are eluted, in order to check repeatability. The third column is used as a blank to detect potential problems related to the stationary phases. The different fractions are separated depending on their affinity to the solvent being used at each step of extraction. Saturated compounds are recovered passing through the column 85 ml of n-pentane.

High Temperature Gas Chromatography (HTGC). The experiments were carried out in a Varian Chrompack CP-3800 chromatograph, equipped with a Varian CP 7542 column 10 meters long, 0.53 mm internal diameter and 0.17 μm stationary phase thick. For detection, a flame ionization detector (FID) with a flame of air and hydrogen at a temperature of 430 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was used. The method is based on the ASTM D-2887 analysis. The samples were diluted in carbon disulfide at a concentration of 5% by weight and injected on column. The carrier gas used was Helium, with a flow of 18 ml/min. The initial temperature of the column oven is 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and it is heated up to 425 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a rate of 16 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Then temperature remains constant for 20 minutes. For calibration of the retention times two different standard n-paraffin mixtures were used: a mixture of C_5 - C_{18} n-paraffins from Agilent Technologies and a C_{20} - C_{70} mixture from Supelco called Poliwax 500.

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$). The equipment used was a Varian Mercury Plus 400 MHz spectrometer. Samples were dissolved in deuterated

chloroform (20 mg in 0.45 ml) using tubes of 5 mm in diameter. A radiofrequency with a pulse of 30 ° was used. A total of 64 scans with 1 s delay was applied.

In this work this technique has been used to determine the aromatic content in each fraction. The weight percent of H_{ar} (hydrogen atoms in aromatic rings), H_α (hydrogen atoms next to functional groups), H_β (methylene hydrogen atoms), and H_γ (methyl hydrogen atoms) were obtained by integration of the corresponding peak areas. The following chemical shift ranges were considered: H_{ar} (9.2–6.5 ppm), H_α (3.8–1.8 ppm), H_β (1.8–1.03 ppm), and H_γ (1.03–0.4 ppm). By comparing the aromatic content of the precipitated fraction and the raw crude oil the trapped crude oil amount of each precipitated fraction was calculated ¹⁶.

Chromatographic separation of trapped crude oil (CS). This method is based on a modification ⁴³ of the sequential elution procedure proposed by Musser and Kilpatrick ¹² and it is used to determine the total wax content of a crude oil. The precipitated solid obtained by Burger's method (known as C₂₀⁺) is dissolved in dichloromethane and the mixture is adsorbed onto silica gel, previously activated at 120 °C overnight. Dichloromethane is removed in an oven at 40 °C. A glass chromatographic column of 1 m long is used. The bottom of the column is charged with fresh activated silica and the top is partially charged with fresh activated alumina and the adsorbed organic matter onto SiO₂ gel. n-Hexane is charged in a 250 ml reservoir attached to the top of the column and it is passed through the column. The cleaned paraffinic compounds are collected after eluting 200 ml of n-hexane.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). Molecular weight determination was carried out in a Waters Alliance 2000 GPCV chromatograph equipped with three chromatographic columns: two columns PLGEL 10 μm Mixed-B, 300 X 7,5 mm and a PLGEL 10 μm 10⁶ Å column. The columns and detectors are kept at 145 ° C. Solvent

was 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene, and a flow rate of 1 ml/min was used. Each sample was analyzed twice in order to check the reproducibility of results.

Thermodynamic model. The precipitation of solids in crude oils at low temperatures is described using an approach previously proposed for alkane mixtures²¹⁻³⁶. The solid-liquid equilibrium equation, relating the composition of component i in the solid and liquid phases, their non ideality, and the thermophysical properties of the pure components³⁹, is given by the next expression:

$$\ln \frac{x_i^s \gamma_i^s}{x_i^l \gamma_i^l} = \frac{\Delta_{fus} H_i}{RT_{fus,i}} \left(\frac{T_{fus,i}}{T} - 1 \right) - \frac{\Delta_{fus} C_{p,i}}{R} \left(1 - \frac{T_{fus,i}}{T} + \ln \frac{T_{fus,i}}{T} \right) \quad (1)$$

where γ_i is the activity coefficient of the i compound, x_i its mole fraction, $\Delta_{fus} H_i(T_{fus})$ the molar enthalpy of fusion of the pure solute at the melting temperature T_{fus} , and $\Delta_{fus} C_{p,i}(T_{fus,i})$ the molar heat capacity change upon fusion, at fusion temperature T_{fus} . The heat capacity change upon fusion is usually regarded as being independent of the temperature and the bracketed term multiplied with $\Delta_{fus} C_{p,m}$ is often considered as being small, as the opposite signs inside the bracket lead to near cancellation⁴⁰. This term was thus neglected on the calculations. The solid phase non-ideality is described by the most recent version of the Predictive UNIQUAC model²⁶. The UNIQUAC model can be written as

$$\frac{g^E}{RT} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln \left(\frac{\Phi_i}{x_i} \right) + \frac{Z}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i x_i \ln \frac{\theta_i}{\Phi_i} - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i q_i \ln \left[\sum_{j=1}^n \theta_j \exp \left(- \frac{\lambda_{ij} - \lambda_{ii}}{q_i RT} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi_i = \frac{x_i r_i}{\sum_j x_j r_j} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_i = \frac{x_i q_i}{\sum_j x_j q_j} \quad (3)$$

Where Φ_i and θ_i are the area and volume fractions, respectively and Z is the coordination number with a value of 10 as in the original UNIQUAC model^{26, 41}. The

structural parameters, r_i and q_i (area and volume parameters, respectively) are obtained from the UNIFAC parameter table ⁴².

The predictive local composition concept ²¹⁻²⁶ allows the estimation of the interaction energies, λ_{ij} , used by these models without fitting to experimental data. The pair interaction energies between two identical molecules are estimated from the heat of sublimation of the pure component,

$$\lambda_{ii} = -\frac{2}{Z}(\Delta_{sub}H_i - RT) \quad (4)$$

The heats of sublimation are calculated at the melting temperature of the pure component as

$$\Delta_{sub}H = \Delta_{vap}H + \Delta_{fus}H \quad (5)$$

The pair interaction energy between two non-identical molecules is given by

$$\lambda_{ij} = \lambda_{ji} = \lambda_{jj} \quad (6)$$

where j is the n-alkane with the shorter chain of the pair ij . The solid-liquid equilibrium model used in this work is thus a purely predictive model that uses only pure component properties for the calculation of the phase equilibria.

3. Results

As previously mentioned, n-paraffin distribution is the input parameter fed to the model used in this work. Paraffin distribution was obtained from saturated compounds of the crude oil obtained by SARA type analysis. The saturate content determined for the crude oil used in this study was 33.8 % by weight. **Figure 1** shows the chromatograms of the raw crude oil and its saturated fraction. Signals with higher intensities correspond to n-paraffins. It is clear that the analysis of the saturated fraction increases signal intensity and allows quantifying the heavier compounds with greater precision.

Besides resolution problems, it is not clear the integration method that should be used. In fact, two different methods have been proposed in literature¹⁰ for obtaining the composition of the n-paraffins: valley to valley integration (Method A) and integration to the baseline of the chromatogram (Method B), both are shown in **Figure 2**. Integration by method A is the most used method in literature, but due to the scarcity of experimental data of wax precipitation in crude oils, predicted results have not been accurately validated.

Figure 3 shows the differences between the n-paraffin distribution obtained by the two integration methods used for the studied crude oil. As seen, n-paraffin obtained from method B is quantitatively higher. This can be explained because method A only considers the areas belonging to n-paraffinic compounds, while, as shown in **Figure 1**, there is a non resolved zone in the chromatogram from the baseline to the start of a valley, which belongs not only to n-paraffins but also to other compounds which can not be identified by means of the up to date techniques. For that reason, the integration by method A subestimates the content of the n-paraffins while it is overestimated by method B.

In spite of obtaining an enhanced signal/noise ratio when saturated fractions are analyzed, it is not enough to solve the resolution problems for high carbon number (C_{38}^+). This point is critical in flow assurance because heavy paraffins have a great influence on the WAT value. For that reason, extrapolation of paraffin composition from C_{38}^+ is proposed as a possible solution. In **Figure 4**, the deviation of n-paraffin composition for heavy paraffin compounds with regard to the expected exponential decay trend can be observed for the crude oil studied.

In this work, the model previously described was used to predict the WPC for the selected crude oil. The model requires as input information the n-paraffin distribution and the molecular weight of the crude oil. In this work, the C_{38}^+ n-paraffin distribution, obtained by extrapolation of the results obtained by the HTGC of saturated compounds using the integration methods A and B, in addition to the molecular weight of the crude oil determined by GPC, were used as input information. In **Figure 5** experimental WPC obtained by fractional precipitation without trapped crude oil discounted by $^1\text{H-NMR}$, WPC obtained by DSC and total wax content at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ obtained by modified Burger's method are compared to thermodynamic model prediction. As can be observed, the thermodynamic model underestimates both WAT and WPC when using the n-paraffin distribution obtained from integration method A as input data. On the contrary, if the n-paraffin distribution obtained by integration method B is used, the thermodynamic model overestimates both magnitudes.

As explained before, the HTGC technique and the equipment used in this work has some limitations and the results provided by the model depend on them. In this work, three variables have been analyzed by using the thermodynamic model previously described to improve the n-paraffin distribution obtained by HTGC: the total amount of

C_{20}^+ paraffin, the extrapolation of paraffin concentration above C_{38}^+ , and the molecular weight of crude oil.

Correction of n-paraffin distribution obtained by integration method A

a) Effect of total amount of paraffin C_{20}^+

The composition of C_{20}^+ n-paraffins obtained by HTGC and integration method A was recalculated in order to check the effect of the total amount of paraffin C_{20}^+ in the WPC predicted by the model. Each individual C_{20}^+ n-paraffin composition was proportionally increased/decreased to make the sum equal to the amount of paraffin obtained experimentally by Burger's method, corrected with the trapped crude oil obtained by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ or CS. The results of the different simulations for the crude oil are shown in **Figure 6**. As can be seen, the model overestimates WPC, compared to the experimental data provided by DSC or fractional precipitation, when n-paraffin distribution is corrected with C_{20}^+ value provided by Burger's method and the trapped crude oil is obtained by CS. Nevertheless, if $^1\text{H-NMR}$ is used to determine trapped crude oil, the differences between predicted and experimental WPC are lower. The chromatographic separation of trapped crude oil allows determining the total saturated content in the precipitated solid, but not exclusively the n-paraffin compounds, which are supposed to be the only ones that precipitate by decreasing temperature. For that reason, the n-paraffin distribution obtained by this method leads to an overestimation of WPC. As it is shown in **Table 1**, Predicted WAT values are underestimated in all cases compared to that provided by DSC.

b) Effect of heavy paraffin composition (C_{38}^+)

To solve the underestimation of the WAT the distribution of n-paraffins obtained by HTGC was extrapolated from C_{38}^+ . **Figure 7** shows the results obtained by applying the model once corrected the n-paraffin distribution with the experimental amount of

paraffin C_{20}^+ and performed the extrapolation of the composition from C_{38}^+ . In this case, as can be observed in **Table 1**, the predicted WAT value is closer to that determined by DSC. However, the WPC is also underestimated if compared to experimental data. As it has been shown, the extrapolation improves the model predictions, and therefore that correction should be included in the n-paraffin distribution obtained by HTGC.

c) Effect of molecular weight of crude oil

The molecular weight is one of the physico-chemical properties of a crude oil that thermodynamic models require to transform the n-paraffin composition provided by HTGC in percentage by weight, into mole fractions used by the model. In this work, the influence of a variation in the molecular weight of about 15 % (approximate error of the methods used to determine this parameter) has been studied. **Figure 8** shows the effect of such variation in molecular weight over model predictions. As can be observed, differences between predicted WPC using molecular weights with a variation of 15 % are minimal. WAT values differs only ± 1 °C.

In spite of the different corrections considered, it was not possible to obtain a good fit between experimental data and predicted values with the n-paraffin distribution obtained from integration method A.

Correction of n-paraffin distribution obtained by integration method B

a) Effect of total amount of paraffin C_{20}^+ and extrapolation from C_{38}^+

To check the effect of the total amount of paraffins C_{20}^+ in the predicted WPC, the n-paraffin distribution obtained by integration method B was corrected as explained before for integration method A. **Figure 9** compares the predictions provided by the thermodynamic model with the experimental results obtained by fractional precipitation and DSC. The model overestimates WPC with regard to the experimental data provided

when n-paraffin distribution is corrected with the amount of C_{20}^+ provided by Burger's method and the trapped crude oil is corrected by CS analysis. The predicted WAT value in this case can be observed in **Table 1**. Nevertheless, if n-paraffin distribution corrected with the C_{20}^+ amount provided by Burger's method and the correction of trapped crude oil by 1H -NMR is used, predicted WPC at low temperatures fits quite well with the experimental data but not the predicted WAT value, as shown in **Table 1**.

b) Correction by fitting experimental WAT obtained by DSC

The previous results show that the extrapolation of C_{38}^+ composition is not enough to minimize the differences between the WAT predicted by the thermodynamic model and the experimental one obtained by DSC as a consequence of heavy paraffin elution problems. For that reason, the n-paraffin distribution obtained from the previous step was corrected again. This correction was carried out in three steps:

1. Determination of the amount of n-paraffin provided by predicted WPC at the WAT value given by DSC.
2. Fitting to zero the composition from the heaviest n-paraffin to the consecutive lighter until the sum of every discounted paraffin was equal to such amount.
3. Normalization of the resulting n-paraffin distribution to C_{20}^+ value provided by Burger's method correcting the trapped crude oil by 1H -NMR.

An iterative procedure was not necessary because the new WAT predicted by the model was very similar to that provided experimentally by DSC in the first stage.

The results of the predictions taking into account the WAT obtained by DSC are shown in **Figure 10**. As can be observed, the predictions obtained in this case are quite good. Predicted WAT value shown in **Table 1** compares favourably with the experimental value provided by DSC.

4. Conclusions

The n-paraffin distribution obtained by HTGC and integration method A was corrected studying the influence of total amount of paraffin C_{20}^+ and extrapolating heavy n-paraffin composition from C_{38}^+ to overcome the limitations of HTGC method, but the prediction in all cases underestimated the WAT and the WPC. However, when the integration method B was applied the predicted WPC compared satisfactory with the experimental curve obtained by fractional precipitation and DSC when correcting the n-paraffin distribution with the total amount of paraffins C_{20}^+ . Only the determination of trapped crude oil by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ gives a reliable experimental total amount of waxes. CS method overestimated in all cases the total wax content and led to wrong predictions.

Although the extrapolation of heavy n-paraffin composition from C_{38}^+ improves predicted WAT results, it is additionally necessary to fit the composition of the heavier n-paraffin with the WAT value obtained by DSC. The molecular weight variation by 15% does not have a significant effect on the predictions.

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Table 1. Experimental and predicted WAT values and WPC

		DSC		METHOD A		METHOD B	
		WAT (°C)	WPC	WAT (°C)	WPC	WAT (°C)	WPC
Experimental		29.4	See Fig. 5	-	-	-	-
Uncorrected n-paraffin distribution		-	-	7	underestimated	49	overestimated
Effect of C ₂₀ ⁺ correction	Corrected with trapped crude oil CS	-	-	16	overestimated	-	-
	Corrected with trapped crude oil NMR	-	-	9	underestimated	-	-
Effect of C ₃₈ ⁺ correction	C ₂₀ ⁺ correction with trapped crude oil CS	-	-	-	-	51	overestimated
	C ₂₀ ⁺ correction with trapped crude oil NMR	-	-	32	underestimated	45	√
WAT _{DSC} fitting		-	-	-	-	33	√

Figure captions

Figure 1. HTGC chromatograms: a) Raw crude oil; b) Saturated fraction separated by SARA analysis.

Figure 2. Different proposed methods of integrating a chromatogram: a) Method A (Valley to valley integration); b) Method B (Integration from valley to the baseline of the chromatogram).

Figure 3. Distribution function (in weight fraction) of n-alkane like components: Integration method A (\circ); Integration method B (\triangle).

Figure 4. Exponential decay trend of n-paraffin distribution: Experimental data (\blacksquare); Exponential decay fit (—).

Figure 5. Total wax content (\blacksquare), experimental WPC fractional precipitation (\blacktriangle); DSC (...) and predicted WPC from both n-paraffin distribution: Integration method A (—); Integration method B (----).

Figure 6. Effect of C_{20}^+ correction in the WPC. *Experimental:* Total wax content trapped crude oil $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (\blacksquare), Total wax content trapped crude oil CS (o); WPC fractional precipitation (\blacktriangle); *Predicted by n-paraffin distribution HTGC (Method A):* uncorrected n-paraffin distribution (—); corrected with trapped crude oil determined by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (----); corrected with trapped crude oil determined by CS (.....).

Figure 7. Effect of paraffin composition from C_{38}^+ in the WPC. *Experimental:* Total wax content trapped crude oil $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (\blacksquare), WPC fractional precipitation (\blacktriangle); *Predicted by n-paraffin distribution HTGC (Method A):* corrected C_{20}^+ with trapped crude oil determined by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (—); extrapolated n-paraffin distribution (----).

Figure 8. Effect of molecular weight of crude oil in the WPC: Total wax content (■), experimental WPC fractional precipitation (▲); GPC molecular weight (—); molecular weight overestimated 15 % (----); molecular weight underestimated 15 % (.....).

Figure 9. Effect of total amount of paraffin C_{20}^+ correction and extrapolation of paraffin composition from C_{38}^+ in the WPC. *Experimental:* Total wax content (■), WPC fractional precipitation (▲); *Predicted by n-paraffin distribution HTGC (Method B):* original n-paraffin distribution (—); corrected with trapped crude oil determined by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (-----); corrected with trapped crude oil determined by CS (.....).

Figure 10. Effect of correction of n-paraffin distribution obtained by method B on predicted WPC. *Experimental:* Total wax content (■), WPC fractional precipitation (▲); WPC_{DSC} (—); *Predicted by n-paraffin distribution HTGC (Method B):* corrected with trapped crude oil determined by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (—); corrected n-paraffin distribution with the experimental WAT_{DSC} (.....).

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Method A

Method B

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

